

Chemical control of brown spot (BS) and sheath rot (ShR) in Tamil Nadu

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To test the efficiency of seven fungicides and three spraying schedules against BS and ShR, a trial with IR20 was laid out in factorial randomized blocks with three replications. Spray schedules were a) 3 on 30, 50, and 70 d after transplanting (DT), b) 2 on 40 and 70 DT, c) need-based, given whenever disease level exceeded grade 3 on the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. The disease level exceeded grade 3 at 77 DT.

Final disease evaluation was taken on 20 samples a week before harvest.

Disease severity (DS) was calculated as:

$$DS = \frac{\text{sum of all numerical ratings} \times 100}{\text{leaf or plant no.} \times \text{maximum scale grade (9)}}$$

and arcsine transformation was used for statistical analysis.

Table 1. Chemical control of BS and ShR on IR20. Tamil Nadu, India.

Chemical	Disease severity ^a (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)
	BS	ShR	
Carbendazim 0.1%	25.4 (30.2)	31.0 (33.8)	4.2
Isoprothiolane 0.1%	27.6 (31.7)	31.3 (34.0)	4.2
Captafol 0.125%	28.1 (32.0)	29.3 (32.8)	4.3
Thiophanate 0.1%	31.8 (34.3)	36.2 (37.0)	4.0
IBP 0.1%	26.1 (30.7)	30.9 (33.7)	4.1
Copper oxychloride 0.25%	32.3 (34.6)	34.5 (36.0)	3.9
Ziram-L 0.3%	33.9 (35.6)	37.9 (38.0)	3.9
No spray	44.3 (41.7)	48.9 (44.4)	3.6
CD (P = 0.05)	1.2	1.1	0.3

^aFigures in parentheses are transformed values.

Table 2. Spraying schedule and control of BS and ShR on IR20. Tamil Nadu, India.

Spraying schedule	Disease severity ^a (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)
	BS	ShR	
30-50-70 DT	28.7 (32.4)	32.7 (34.9)	4.1
40-70 DT	31.7 (34.3)	35.1 (36.3)	4.0
At need (77 DT)	32.7 (34.9)	36.9 (37.4)	4.0
CD (P = 0.05)	0.7	0.7	0.2

^aAv of 7 treatments with different chemicals. Figures in parentheses are transformed values.

The interaction between chemicals and spray schedules was not significant. Captafol 0.125% had the lowest ShR severity (29.3%) and maximum yield (4.3 t/ha) (Table 1). Carbendazim 0.1% had the lowest BS severity, 25.4%.

Yields were not significantly different.

Spraying 30, 50, and 70 DT controlled disease severity the best (Table 2). Differences in yield were not significant. *SI*

Reaction of tungro (RTV) isolates on Taichung Native 1

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Five RTV isolates from Aduthurai (Tamil Nadu), Pusa (Bihar), Cuttack (Orissa) and Malda and Hooghly (West Bengal) were collected and maintained on rice cultivar Jaya. Twenty 15-d-old TN1 seedlings were inoculated with each isolate at 1 and 5 leafhoppers/seedling. In another experiment, 20-d-old TN1 seedlings were inoculated with each isolate at 5 insects/seedling. The seedlings were transplanted in galvanized iron trays. Percentage of reduction in plant height and tiller number were measured 60 d after inoculation. Plants with

typical symptoms were selected for each isolate and serologically indexed for virus infection.

RTBV (bacilliform) and RTSV (spherical) particles were present in all plants infected with each isolate. There was not much difference in infection at 1 and 5 leafhoppers per plant, except in the Malda isolate, which had lower infection (see table). The isolates from

Pusa and Cuttack caused more severe stunting and reduced the number of tillers. Stunting and tiller reduction were less in the Aduthurai isolate. The Hooghly and Malda isolates showed intermediate stunting. The isolates have been tentatively designated RTV-1 (Aduthurai), RTV-2 (Pusa and Cuttack), and RTV-3 (Hooghly and Malda). *SI*

Reaction of TN1 to infection with RTV isolates. Cuttack, India.

	Leafhoppers (no.) used for inoculation	Reaction (%) to RTV isolates				
		Pusa	Aduthurai	Cuttack	Hooghly	Malda
Infection	1	75	83	70	78	48
	5	100	100	100	100	100
Stunting	5	94	28	82	43	35
Reduction in tiller number	5	98	27	92	67	50